
ON MULLIN'S SECOND SEQUENCE OF PRIMES

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Abstract

We consider the second of Mullin's sequences of prime numbers related to Euclid's proof that there are infinitely many primes. We show in particular that it omits infinitely many primes, confirming a conjecture of Cox and van der Poorten.

1. Introduction

In [10], Mullin constructed two sequences of prime numbers related to Euclid's proof that there are infinitely many primes. For the first sequence, say $\{p_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, we take $p_1 = 2$ and define p_{n+1} to be the smallest prime factor of $1 + p_1 \cdots p_n$. The second sequence, $\{P_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, is defined similarly, except that we replace the words "smallest prime factor" by "largest prime factor". These are sequences A000945 and A000946 in the OEIS [13], and the first few terms of each are shown below.

Table 1: First ten terms of Mullin's sequences

n	p_n	P_n
1	2	2
2	3	3
3	7	7
4	43	43
5	13	139
6	53	50207
7	5	340999
8	6221671	2365347734339
9	38709183810571	4680225641471129
10	139	1368845206580129

Mullin then asked whether every prime is contained in each of these sequences, and if not, whether they are recursive, i.e., whether there is an algorithm to decide

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if a given prime occurs or not.² Almost nothing related to this is known for the first sequence, though Shanks [14] conjectured on probabilistic grounds that it contains every prime; we briefly discuss this conjecture and some variants in Section 2 below. Concerning the second sequence, Cox and van der Poorten [3] showed that, apart from the first four terms 2, 3, 7 and 43, it omits all the primes less than 53; it is straightforward to extend this to the remaining primes less than 79 by applying their method using the most recent computations of P_n , due of Wagstaff [15]. In response to Mullin's questions, Cox and van der Poorten conjectured that infinitely many primes are omitted, and that their method would always work to decide whether a given prime occurs; moreover, they showed that at least one of their conjectures is true. The main point of this paper is to prove the first of these conjectures. Precisely, we show the following.

Theorem 1. *The sequence $\{P_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ omits infinitely many primes. If $\{Q_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ denotes the sequence of omitted primes in increasing order, then*

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log Q_{n+1}}{\log(Q_1 \cdots Q_n)} \leq \frac{1}{4\sqrt{e}-1} = 0.1787\dots$$

We note that although our method of proof allows us to bound each omitted prime Q_n in terms of the previous ones, it is not constructive; in particular, Mullin's second question remains open (see Theorem 2 below, however).

The number $\frac{1}{4\sqrt{e}-1}$ above is related to the best known bound $O\left(p^{\frac{1}{4\sqrt{e}}+o(1)}\right)$ for the least quadratic non-residue (mod p). This was first shown by Burgess [1], based on an argument of Vinogradov; apart from refinements of the $o(1)$, it has not been improved upon in over 50 years. However, if the Generalized Riemann Hypothesis for quadratic Dirichlet L -functions is true then one can show the much stronger bound $Q_{n+1} = O(\log^2(Q_1 \cdots Q_n))$, from which it follows that

$$\#\{n : Q_n \leq x\} \gg \frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log x}$$

for large x . Even this seems far from the truth; indeed, it is likely that the set of primes that occur in $\{P_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ has density 0. While we have not been able to prove that unconditionally, by refining Cox and van der Poorten's argument on the relationship between their conjectures, we can show the following.

Theorem 2. *If $\{P_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ is not recursive then it has logarithmic density 0 in the primes, i.e.,*

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{\substack{p \leq x \\ p \in \{P_1, P_2, \dots\}}} \frac{1}{p}}{\sum_{\substack{p \leq x \\ p \text{ prime}}} \frac{1}{p}} = 0.$$

²Mullin also asked whether the second sequence might be monotonic (and hence recursive); this was answered negatively by Naur [11], who was the first to compute it beyond the 9th term. However, it remains an open question whether there are infinitely many n such that $P_n > P_{n+1}$.

2. Variants

Before embarking on the proofs of Theorems 1 and 2, we set our results in context by comparing to a few variants of the sequence $\{P_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$.

1. As mentioned above, very little is known about Mullin's first sequence $\{p_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$. Shanks reasoned that as n increases, the numbers $t_n = p_1 \cdots p_n$ should vary randomly among the invertible residues classes $(\text{mod } p)$ for any fixed prime p , until p occurs in the sequence, after which point $t_n \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. If p does not occur then this is violated, since t_n is always invertible $(\text{mod } p)$ but falls into the residue class of -1 at most finitely many times. As no one has found any reason to suggest that t_n does not vary randomly $(\text{mod } p)$, this is certainly compelling. However, there is reason to tread cautiously, first because Kurokawa and Satoh [7] have shown that an analogue of this conjecture for the Euclidean domains $\mathbb{F}_p[x]$ is false in general, and second because of what happens in the next variant that we consider.
2. In the second variant, instead of just introducing one new prime at each step, we add in all prime divisors of 1 plus the product of the previously constructed primes. In symbols, we set $S_0 = \emptyset$ and define S_n recursively by

$$S_{n+1} = S_n \cup \left\{ p : p \text{ prime and } p \mid \left(1 + \prod_{s \in S_n} s \right) \right\}.$$

This is related to Sylvester's sequence $\{s_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$, defined by $s_n = 1 + \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} s_i$, or equivalently, $s_0 = 2$, $s_{n+1} = 1 + s_n(s_n - 1)$. More precisely, there is empirical evidence to suggest that s_n is always squarefree, and if that is the case then

$$\prod_{p \in S_n} p = \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} s_i.$$

In particular, each prime that we construct this way divides some Sylvester number. One could try applying the same sort reasoning as in Shanks' conjecture for this sequence, but it turns out that there is a conspiracy preventing this from working, since s_n can be described by a one-step recurrence. In fact, Odoni [12] showed that the set of primes dividing a Sylvester number has density 0. Thus, perhaps counterintuitively, the greedy algorithm of adding in all prime divisors likely yields a very thin subset of the primes.

3. Pomerance considered the following variant (unpublished, but see [4, §1.1.3]). Let $r_1 = 2$, and define r_{n+1} recursively to be the smallest prime number which is not one of r_1, \dots, r_n and divides a number of the form $d + 1$, where $d \mid r_1 \cdots r_n$. This is in some sense even greedier than the previous variant, but

the fact that we can choose proper divisors d of $r_1 \cdots r_n$ prevents the numbers from growing out of control. Thus, Pomerance showed that every prime does indeed occur in this sequence, and in fact r_n is just the n th prime number for $n \geq 5$.

4. Each variant has an analogue with the $+1$ in the definition replaced by -1 . For instance, Selfridge (unpublished, but see [5]) considered the sequence $\{\tilde{P}_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ where $\tilde{P}_1 = 3$ and \tilde{P}_{n+1} is the largest prime factor of $\tilde{P}_1 \cdots \tilde{P}_n - 1$. He showed that it omits some primes, analogous to the result of Cox and van der Poorten for $\{P_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$. Likewise, with some small modifications to the proof, it is not hard to see that Theorem 1 remains true with $\{P_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ replaced by $\{\tilde{P}_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$.

3. Proofs

We begin by reviewing the method of [3]. For a positive integer n , suppose that $1 + P_1 \cdots P_n$ has the factorization

$$1 + P_1 \cdots P_n = q_1^{k_1} \cdots q_r^{k_r}, \tag{*}$$

where $q_1 < \dots < q_r$ are prime and $q_r = P_{n+1}$. Observe that the left-hand side is $\equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, so that

$$\left(\frac{-4}{q_1}\right)^{k_1} \cdots \left(\frac{-4}{q_r}\right)^{k_r} = -1,$$

where $\left(\frac{a}{b}\right)$ denotes the Kronecker symbol. Similarly, if d is a fundamental discriminant dividing $P_1 \cdots P_n$ then the left-hand side is $\equiv 1 \pmod{d}$, so that

$$\left(\frac{d}{q_1}\right)^{k_1} \cdots \left(\frac{d}{q_r}\right)^{k_r} = 1.$$

Cox and van der Poorten considered values of d for which $|d|$ is one of the known P_i , thus obtaining a system of equations which they attempted to solve by linear algebra over \mathbb{F}_2 . As more of the P_i become known, one adds more and more constraints that must be satisfied by the small primes q which have not yet occurred, and one can hope eventually to reach an inconsistent system. There is no known reason to believe that the equations for the various P_i are related, and this motivates their conjectures.

An equivalent formulation of their method is to look for a fundamental discriminant d composed of known P_i such that $\left(\frac{d}{q}\right) = \left(\frac{-4}{q}\right)$ for the first several primes q which are not known to occur. This is the approach that we will take, as outlined in the following lemmas.

Lemma 3. *Let $\chi \pmod{q}$ be a non-principal quadratic character, not necessarily primitive. Then there is a prime number $n \ll_\varepsilon q^{\frac{1}{4\sqrt{\varepsilon}} + \varepsilon}$ such that $\chi(n) = -1$.*

Proof. Let n be the smallest positive integer such that $\chi(n) = -1$. It is clear that n must be prime, so it suffices to prove the upper bound. This is essentially a special case of [8, Theorem 1], except for the technical point that q need not be cubefree.

To circumvent that, we factor $\chi = \chi_0\chi_1$ where $\chi_0 \pmod{q_0}$ is trivial and $\chi_1 \pmod{q_1}$ is a primitive quadratic character. Note that if we replace q_0 by $q'_0 = \prod_{p|q_0} p$ and χ_0 by the trivial character $\chi'_0 \pmod{q'_0}$, then $\chi' = \chi'_0\chi_1$ satisfies $\chi'(m) = \chi(m)$ for every m . Thus, we may assume without loss of generality that q_0 is squarefree and $(q_0, q_1) = 1$.

Moreover, $\pm q_1$ is a fundamental discriminant, so in fact $q = q_0q_1$ is cubefree except possibly for a factor of 8. Even if $8|q$, one can see that Burgess' bounds [2, Theorem 2], on which [8, Theorem 1] is based, continue to hold at the expense of a worse implied constant. (See [6, (12.56)] for a precise statement of this type.) The result follows. \square

Lemma 4. *Let q_1, \dots, q_r be pairwise relatively prime positive integers. For each $i = 1, \dots, r$, let $\chi_i \pmod{q_i}$ be a non-principal quadratic character, not necessarily primitive, and let $\epsilon_i \in \{\pm 1\}$. Then there is a squarefree positive integer n with at most r prime factors, each $\ll_\epsilon (q_1 \cdots q_r)^{\frac{1}{4\sqrt{\epsilon}} + \epsilon}$, such that $\chi_i(n) = \epsilon_i$ for all $i = 1, \dots, r$.*

Proof. Let ψ_i be the principal character $\pmod{q_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$, and set $q = q_1 \cdots q_r$. For each non-empty subset $S \subset \{1, \dots, r\}$ we define a character $\chi_S \pmod{q}$ by

$$\chi_S(n) = \prod_{i=1}^r \begin{cases} \chi_i(n) & \text{if } i \in S, \\ \psi_i(n) & \text{if } i \notin S. \end{cases}$$

Note that χ_S must be non-trivial since the q_i are pairwise relatively prime. By Lemma 1, there is a prime $n_S \ll_\epsilon q^{\frac{1}{4\sqrt{\epsilon}} + \epsilon}$ such that $\chi_S(n_S) = -1$. Further, we associate to S two vectors in \mathbb{F}_2^r . The first is the characteristic vector $v_S = (a_1, \dots, a_r)$, defined by

$$a_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \in S, \\ 0 & \text{if } i \notin S. \end{cases}$$

The second is the unique vector $w_S = (b_1, \dots, b_r)$ such that $\chi_i(n_S) = (-1)^{b_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$. These vectors have scalar product $v_S \cdot w_S = 1$ since $\chi_S(n_S) = -1$.

We claim that $\{w_S : \emptyset \neq S \subset \{1, \dots, r\}\}$ spans \mathbb{F}_2^r . If not then there would be a non-zero linear functional which vanishes at each such w_S , i.e., a non-zero $v \in \mathbb{F}_2^r$ with $v \cdot w_S = 0$ for all $S \neq \emptyset$. However, this is impossible since the v_S exhaust all non-zero vectors in \mathbb{F}_2^r .

Therefore, there is a set T of non-empty subsets of $\{1, \dots, r\}$ such that $\{w_S : S \in T\}$ is a basis for \mathbb{F}_2^r . It follows that the numbers n_S for $S \in T$ are distinct

primes, and as n ranges over the divisors of $\prod_{S \in T} n_S$, $(\chi_1(n), \dots, \chi_r(n))$ ranges over all elements of $\{\pm 1\}^r$. \square

3.1. Proof of Theorem 1

Let Q_1, \dots, Q_r be the first r omitted primes. (We allow $r = 0$ to start the argument, with the understanding that $Q_1 \cdots Q_r = 1$ in that case.) Suppose that all other primes up to some number $x \geq 3$ eventually occur, and let $p = P_{n+1} \leq x$ be the last to occur. Then except for Q_1, \dots, Q_r , all primes below p must occur before p , so (*) takes the form

$$1 + P_1 \cdots P_n = Q_1^{k_1} \cdots Q_r^{k_r} \cdot p^k$$

for some $k, k_1, \dots, k_r \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$. Now, applying Lemma 2 with the characters

$$\left(\frac{-4}{\cdot}\right), \left(\frac{\cdot}{p}\right) \text{ and } \left(\frac{\cdot}{Q_1}\right), \dots, \left(\frac{\cdot}{Q_r}\right),$$

we can find a squarefree positive integer $d \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ such that

$$\left(\frac{d}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{-4}{p}\right), \left(\frac{d}{Q_i}\right) = \left(\frac{-4}{Q_i}\right) \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, r,$$

and with all prime factors of d bounded by $O_\varepsilon\left((pQ_1 \cdots Q_r)^{\frac{1}{4\sqrt{e}} + \varepsilon}\right)$. Since $p \leq x$ and $\frac{1}{4\sqrt{e}} < 1$, this bound must fall below x for large enough x , and in fact it is not hard to see that there is such an $x \ll_\varepsilon (Q_1 \cdots Q_r)^{\frac{1}{4\sqrt{e}-1} + \varepsilon}$. This is a contradiction, and thus there must be another omitted prime $Q_{r+1} \ll_\varepsilon (Q_1 \cdots Q_r)^{\frac{1}{4\sqrt{e}-1} + \varepsilon}$. \square

The proof of Theorem 2 is based on the following generalization of the method of Cox and van der Poorten. For each $i = 1, 2, \dots$, let g_i be the smallest positive primitive root (mod P_i^2), and let $l_i : (\mathbb{Z}/P_i^2\mathbb{Z})^\times \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/P_i(P_i - 1)\mathbb{Z}$ be the base- g_i logarithm. Suppose that we have computed P_1, \dots, P_N . Note that if $n \geq N$ then for any $i \leq N$, the left-hand side of (*) is $\equiv 1 \pmod{P_i}$ but $\not\equiv 1 \pmod{P_i^2}$ since the P 's are distinct. Thus, $k_1 l_i(q_1) + \dots + k_r l_i(q_r) \equiv 0 \pmod{P_i - 1}$, but is non-zero (mod P_i). In other words, there is a vector $b_i \in \mathbb{F}_{P_i}^r$ such that $b_i \cdot (k_1, \dots, k_r) \neq 0 \in \mathbb{F}_{P_i}$. On the other hand, we can construct other constraints (mod P_i) by considering (*) modulo any P_j for which $P_j \equiv 1 \pmod{P_i}$ (if there are any). If P_j is such a prime then $k_1 l_j(q_1) + \dots + k_r l_j(q_r) \equiv 0 \pmod{P_i}$, i.e., there is a vector $v_{ij} \in \mathbb{F}_{P_i}^r$ such that $v_{ij} \cdot (k_1, \dots, k_r) = 0 \in \mathbb{F}_{P_i}$.

Thus, we can try to prove that q_r is omitted by finding a linear combination of the v_{ij} which yields b_i . For $i = 1$, this is equivalent to Cox and van der Poorten's method. If that fails to exclude q_r then we can try $i = 2$, and so on. Note that from a practical standpoint, one will accumulate equations modulo $P_1 = 2$ far more quickly than for the other primes. Thus, the greatest chance of success is with $i = 1$,

so this is unlikely to yield any improvement over their method in practice. However, as our proof will show, the other primes become useful if there is a conspiracy which makes their method fail.

Lemma 5. *Let n be a squarefree positive integer, q an integer which is relatively prime to n and not a perfect p th power for any prime $p|n$, and d a divisor of n . Then the field $L = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[d]{q}, e^{2\pi i/n})$ is normal over \mathbb{Q} and has degree $[L : \mathbb{Q}] = d\varphi(n)$. Further, a rational prime p not dividing the discriminant of L splits completely in L if and only if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ and $\exists x \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $x^d \equiv q \pmod{p}$.*

Proof (adapted from [9], Lemmas 3.1 and 3.2). First note that L is the splitting field of $(x^d - q)(x^n - 1)$, so it is normal over \mathbb{Q} . Set $\zeta_n = e^{2\pi i/n}$, and let $K = \mathbb{Q}(\zeta_n)$ be the corresponding cyclotomic field. Then K has degree $\varphi(n)$ over \mathbb{Q} , so to establish the formula for $[L : \mathbb{Q}] = [L : K][K : \mathbb{Q}]$, it suffices to show that $x^d - q$ is irreducible over K .

To that end, we first show that $\sqrt[p]{q} \notin K$ for any prime divisor $p|d$. If p is odd then $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{q}) \subset \mathbb{R}$ is not normal over \mathbb{Q} since it has non-real conjugates. On the other hand, every subfield of K is normal over \mathbb{Q} since K is an abelian extension, and thus $\sqrt[p]{q} \notin K$. This argument fails if $p = 2$, but in that case it follows from class field theory that the quadratic subfields of K are exactly those of the form $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{D})$ for fundamental discriminants $D|n$. Since $(q, n) = 1$, $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{q})$ is not among them, so the claim still holds.

Next, suppose that $f \in K[x]$ is a monic irreducible factor of $x^d - q$, of degree $d' < d$. Note that over L we have the factorization

$$x^d - q = \prod_{j=1}^d (x - \zeta_d^j \sqrt[d]{q}),$$

where $\zeta_d = \zeta_n^{n/d}$ is a primitive d th root of unity. Thus, the constant term of f must take the form $(-1)^{d'} \zeta_n^k q^{d'/d}$ for some integer k . Hence $q^{d'/d} \in K$, and by the Euclidean algorithm we can improve this to $q^{(d',d)/d} \in K$. However, since $0 \neq d' < d$, there is a prime $p | \frac{d}{(d',d)}$. This implies that $\sqrt[p]{q} \in K$, in contradiction to the above, and thus $x^d - q$ is irreducible over K , as claimed.

For the final statement, it is well-known that a rational prime p splits completely in $K = \mathbb{Q}(\zeta_n)$ if and only if $p \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$, and this is a necessary condition for p to split completely in $L \supset K$. If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$, let \mathfrak{p} be any of the $\varphi(n)$ primes of K dividing $p\mathfrak{o}_K$, where \mathfrak{o}_K is the ring of integers of K . If p does not divide the discriminant of L then \mathfrak{p} splits completely in L if and only if $x^d - q$ has d roots in the residue field $\mathfrak{o}_K/\mathfrak{p} \cong \mathbb{F}_p$, which in turn happens if and only if q has a d th root \pmod{p} . \square

Lemma 6. *Let m be a squarefree positive integer and q an integer which is relatively*

prime to m and not a perfect p th power for any prime $p|m$. Then the set of primes p for which $x^m \equiv q \pmod{p}$ is solvable has natural density $\frac{\varphi(m)}{m}$.

Proof. Note that the number of solutions of $x^m \equiv q \pmod{p}$ is the same as that of $x^{(m,p-1)} \equiv q \pmod{p}$. For large $y > 0$, we thus want to estimate the fraction

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\pi(y)} \sum_{p \leq y} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x^{(m,p-1)} \equiv q \pmod{p} \text{ is solvable,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \sum_{d|m} \frac{1}{\pi(y)} \sum_{\substack{p \leq y \\ (m,p-1)=d}} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x^d \equiv q \pmod{p} \text{ is solvable,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \sum_{d|m} \sum_{e|\frac{m}{d}} \mu(e) \frac{1}{\pi(y)} \sum_{\substack{p \leq y \\ p \equiv 1 \pmod{de}}} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x^d \equiv q \pmod{p} \text{ is solvable,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \sum_{n|m} \sum_{d|n} \mu\left(\frac{n}{d}\right) \frac{1}{\pi(y)} \sum_{\substack{p \leq y \\ p \equiv 1 \pmod{n}}} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x^d \equiv q \pmod{p} \text{ is solvable,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 3 and the Chebotarev Density Theorem, the inner sum over p divided by $\pi(y)$ tends to $\frac{1}{d\varphi(n)}$ as $y \rightarrow \infty$. (Note that the earlier Kronecker-Frobenius Density Theorem would be enough here if we instead considered the logarithmic density.) Thus, the set we are interested in has density

$$\sum_{n|m} \sum_{d|n} \frac{\mu(n/d)}{d\varphi(n)} = \sum_{n|m} \frac{\mu(n)}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{d|n} \frac{\mu(d)}{d} = \sum_{n|m} \frac{\mu(n)}{n} = \frac{\varphi(m)}{m}.$$

□

3.2. Proof of Theorem 2

Since $\{P_j\}_{j=1}^\infty$ is recursively enumerable, the only way that it can fail to be recursive is if there is some Q_r for which there is no algorithm to prove that it does not occur among the P_j . In particular, the general strategy described above must fail to exclude Q_r , no matter how large we take N .

Note that for large enough N , (*) will take the form

$$1 + P_1 \cdots P_n = Q_1^{k_1} \cdots Q_r^{k_r}$$

for $n \geq N$. For $i = 1, \dots, N$, let $b_i, v_{ij} \in \mathbb{F}_{P_i}^*$ be as described above. Although we have restricted to $i \leq N$, we are free to consider arbitrarily large values of j in this construction by taking $n \geq j$ in (*), so for each i there are potentially infinitely many suitable j . In order to avoid eventually concluding that Q_r is omitted, b_i

must not be a linear combination of the v_{ij} ; in particular, the v_{ij} span a proper subspace of $\mathbb{F}_{P_i}^r$, so there is a non-zero vector $w_i \in \mathbb{F}_{P_i}^r$ such that $v_{ij} \cdot w_i = 0$ for every j such that $P_j \equiv 1 \pmod{P_i}$. By the Chinese Remainder Theorem, there are non-negative integers $a_1, \dots, a_r < P_1 \cdots P_N$ such that $(a_1, \dots, a_r) \equiv w_i \pmod{P_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$. Set $q = Q_1^{a_1} \cdots Q_r^{a_r}$. Then by construction, q is not a perfect P_i th power for any $i \leq N$, but it is a P_i th power residue $\pmod{P_j}$ for all j such that $P_j \equiv 1 \pmod{P_i}$. Note also that q is automatically a P_i th power residue $\pmod{P_j}$ if $P_j \not\equiv 1 \pmod{P_i}$.

It follows that the entire sequence $\{P_j : j = 1, 2, \dots\}$ is a subset of the primes modulo which q is an m th power residue, where $m = P_1 \cdots P_N$. By Lemma 4, that set has density

$$\frac{\varphi(m)}{m} = \prod_{i=1}^N \left(1 - \frac{1}{P_i}\right).$$

Taking N arbitrarily large, we have

$$\limsup_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\#\{j : P_j \leq x\}}{\pi(x)} \leq \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{P_i}\right),$$

with the understanding that the right-hand side is 0 if the product diverges. In that case, $\{P_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ has natural density 0, which in turn implies that the logarithmic density is 0. On the other hand, if the product converges then so does $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{P_i}$, which also implies that the logarithmic density is 0.

Finally, we remark that while it does not necessarily follow that $\{P_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ has a natural density, the last inequality shows that its upper density is strictly less than 1; in fact, using just the values in Table 1, we see that the upper density is at most 0.277056. \square

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